

Research Article

Innovation and Collaboration: Empowering SMEs and Startups in the Technology Sector through BizConnect

Nur Artasha Amran¹, Hasya Afiqah Ramli², Maisarah Sharidan³, Mohd Syafiq Mohd Sidik⁴, Nurul Suhada Aziz⁵, Mazlina Mamat⁶, Nur Haslina Ramli⁷, and Mariam Setapa^{8,*}

¹ Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School, UiTM Kelantan; nurartasha@gmail.com

² Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School, UiTM Kelantan; hasyaafiqah157@gmail.com

³ Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School, UiTM Kelantan; mysarahshrdn95@gmail.com

⁴ Arshad Ayub Graduate Business School, UiTM Kelantan; mohdsyafiqmohdsidik@gmail.com

⁵ College of Computing, Informatics and Mathematics Studies, UiTM Kelantan; nurulsuhada@uitm.edu.my

⁶ Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Kelantan; mzlina@uitm.edu.my

⁷ Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Kelantan; haslina581@uitm.edu.my

⁸ Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Kelantan; maria135@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2151-7909>)

* Correspondence: maria135@uitm.edu.my; +6013 724 2641

Abstract: BizConnect is a new and innovative platform that helps SMEs and startups in the technology and innovation sectors to network and collaborate. BizConnect solves the problems that SMEs and startups face when they look for networking solutions that support collaboration and innovation. BizConnect is different from other networking platforms because it has features that suit the needs of businesses in the technology and innovation sectors. The platform combines networking tools and a focus on meaningful collaborations to stand out from other platforms. The platform's main features are a project collaboration space, a resource exchange hub, and an event management system. BizConnect wants to give users a better and more valuable experience by using these features. The platform's value is based on its networking tools and its focus on meaningful collaborations in the technology and innovation sectors. Moreover, BizConnect makes a positive difference in the society and economy by giving businesses a platform to connect, collaborate, and grow. The platform's goal is to connect people who think alike and create a lively entrepreneurial community.

Keywords: Recycle; Plastic Waste; Pollution; Environmental Awareness; Durability; Sustainability

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1. INTRODUCTION

BizConnect is a revolutionary networking and collaboration platform designed to meet the specific needs of SMEs and startups in the technology and innovation sectors. The platform offers a comprehensive suite of features, including curated industry events, expert content, and seamless collaboration tools, to foster innovation and growth among businesses. BizConnect was invented to address the challenges faced by SMEs and startups in accessing advanced networking solutions that foster collaboration and innovation. According to Roman & Rusu, (2022), the process of digitization has the impact of diminishing transaction costs, providing improved and faster access to information, and enhancing communication among employees, suppliers, and networks. Additionally, it catalyzes for SMEs to seamlessly integrate into global markets, as it reduces the expenses related to transportation

and border operations. The digitalization trend facilitates enterprises in accessing various resources, including financial support, training opportunities, and recruitment channels, many of which are increasingly transitioning to online platforms. Furthermore, it plays a pivotal role in supporting innovation and expanding access to innovation assets. Digitalization empowers enterprises to generate and analyze data in innovative ways, enabling them to enhance their operational performance significantly.

Unlike traditional networking platforms, BizConnect offers tailored features that cater to the specific needs of businesses in the technology and innovation sectors. The platform's unique blend of comprehensive networking tools and a focus on fostering meaningful collaborations within the technology and innovation sectors sets it apart from conventional networking platforms. The platform's main features include a dynamic project collaboration space, resource exchange hub, and event management system. By encouraging users to fully embrace these features, BizConnect aims to provide a more comprehensive and valuable experience, distinguishing itself from conventional networking platforms. The platform's value proposition revolves around its unique blend of comprehensive networking tools and a focus on fostering meaningful collaborations within the technology and innovation sectors.

According to *The Digital Transformation of SMEs.*, (2021), employing digital tools yields substantial advantages for businesses. The process of digitization plays a pivotal role in reducing transaction costs by facilitating improved and faster access to information, fostering efficient communication among staff, suppliers, and networks. SMEs can leverage digitalization to seamlessly integrate into global markets, benefiting from reduced costs associated with transportation and border operations, thereby expanding opportunities for trading services. Digital tools further simplify access to various resources, encompassing finance through platforms like peer-to-peer lending, training opportunities, and recruitment channels, including government services increasingly transitioning to online platforms. Additionally, digitalization fosters innovation, providing broader access to innovation assets. It also empowers businesses to generate and analyze data in novel ways, thereby driving enhanced operational performance.

Furthermore, BizConnect has a significant impact on the socio-economic environment by providing a platform for businesses to connect, collaborate, and grow. The pace of economic operations has undergone a profound transformation due to digital technology. The internet and digital devices stand out as catalysts for driving economic growth (Afonasova et al., 2019). Positive contributions to economic growth stem from increased productivity due to the implementation of more streamlined business processes supported by Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). Additionally, growth in revenue is achieved through expanded market reach. There is also an influence on the structure and deployment of industrial value chains. Furthermore, certain sectors within the services industry, such as software development and business process outsourcing, experience substantial growth (Raul L. Katz Social and Economic Impact of Digital Transformation on the Economy, n.d.).

The platform's mission is to connect like-minded individuals and foster a vibrant entrepreneurial community. By achieving a substantial 30% increase in user registrations within the first six months, BizConnect aims to expand its user base and establish a thriving network of entrepreneurs who can leverage its unique offerings for collaboration and growth. Indeed, the surge of digital innovation has profoundly influenced the functioning of businesses, with a notable impact on SMEs. Leveraging digital technology, SMEs have gained access to untapped markets, enhanced their operational effectiveness, and fostered the creation of innovative products and services. Consequently, SMEs have emerged as pivotal contributors to economic growth and the generation of employment opportunities in numerous countries (Sirait et al., 2023).

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

There's a lack of good networking platforms for small and startup tech and innovation businesses. The ones that exist are too general and don't give these businesses what they really need to succeed (i.e SME Connex and SME Colony). SMEs need a platform that's more than just regular networking. It should also help them collaborate, share knowledge, and grow fast (SMEs in the World of Cyber.,2022) Small and startup tech and innovation businesses face a big challenge. Most of them don't have enough resources and expertise (Saunila, M., 2014). They work with tight budgets and can't afford to hire full-time staff or invest in expensive tools and technologies. This makes it hard for them to compete with bigger businesses and stay on top. Regular networking platforms such as government agency not all provide the support and expertise these businesses need to grow and succeed (Valentina Dardha., 2004). Another problem for these businesses is the lack of industry-specific networking events. The usual events are too general and don't focus on what tech and innovation businesses really need (Voss, G., 2012). This makes it tough for entrepreneurs to connect with others like them, limiting their chances to grow. Moreover, regular networking platforms are often confusing and hard to use. Entrepreneurs struggle to find the resources and expertise they need. These platforms don't have the right tools and features to help collaboration and knowledge-sharing, limiting innovation and growth (DeVito, M. A., Birnholtz, J., & Hancock, J. T., 2017)

3. PRODUCT DESCRIPTION

Figure 1. Login page and sign up page .

Figure 2. Reset password and home page .

Figure 3. Information page.

Figure 4. Search and forum page.

Figure 5. Event and network page.

Figure 6. Group and chat page.

BizConnect is a comprehensive networking and collaboration platform designed for SMEs and startups in the technology and innovation sectors. The platform offers a suite of tools to facilitate collaboration, knowledge sharing, and business growth. BizConnect's core product is a user-friendly platform that allows entrepreneurs to showcase their skills, projects, and business ventures. The platform's key features include a dynamic project collaboration space, a resource exchange hub, and an event management system. The project collaboration space enables entrepreneurs to find like-minded individuals or businesses for joint ventures. Users can create and manage projects, invite collaborators, and track progress within the platform. The resource exchange hub allows entrepreneurs to share resources such as expertise, tools, or services, fostering a collaborative and supportive community.

BizConnect's event management system facilitates the organization and promotion of networking events, webinars, and workshops. Integrated communication tools enable real-time interactions between entrepreneurs, making it easier to connect, collaborate, and learn from one another. The platform's interface is clean, modern, and user-friendly, reflecting the professional nature of entrepreneurial endeavors. Profiles are visually appealing, allowing entrepreneurs to highlight their achievements, skills, and ongoing projects. The platform incorporates vibrant colors and intuitive navigation to create an engaging user experience. Overall, BizConnect is a comprehensive networking platform that fosters collaboration and innovation among businesses in the technology and innovation sectors.

4. FUNCTIONAL SPECIFICATION OF PRODUCT INNOVATION

BizConnect's product innovation is designed to provide a comprehensive networking platform that goes beyond traditional networking to facilitate collaboration, knowledgesharing, and rapid business growth among businesses in the technology and innovation sectors. Functional specifications of BizConnect's product innovation can be summarized as follows: 1. User-friendly profiles: BizConnect offers user-friendly profiles that allow entrepreneurs to showcase their skills, projects, and business ventures. 2. Dynamic project collaboration space: The platform's project collaboration space enables entrepreneurs to find like-minded individuals or businesses for joint ventures. Users can create and manage projects, invite collaborators, and track progress within the platform. 3. Resource exchange hub: BizConnect's resource exchange hub allows entrepreneurs to share resources such as expertise, tools, or services, fostering a collaborative and supportive community. 4. Event management system: The platform's event management system facilitates the organization and promotion of networking events, webinars, and workshops. Integrated communication tools enable real-time interactions between entrepreneurs, making it easier to connect, collaborate, and learn from one another. 5. Curated content: BizConnect offers curated content that is specifically tailored to address the unique needs of SMEs and startups in the technology and innovation sectors. 6. Industry-specific networking events: The platform offers industry-specific networking events that enable entrepreneurs to connect with like-minded individuals and businesses. 7. Comprehensive suite of tools: BizConnect's comprehensive suite of tools aligns seamlessly with the aspirations and challenges of SMEs and startups in the technology sector, positioning it as the ideal solution for fostering meaningful connections and driving innovation.

5. NOVELTY AND UNIQUENESS OF THE PRODUCT

BizConnect's novelty and uniqueness lie in providing a comprehensive networking platform that goes beyond traditional networking to facilitate collaboration, knowledgesharing, and rapid business growth among businesses in the technology and innovation sectors. The platform's tailored features, curated content, industry-specific networking events, and user-friendly interface position it as the premier destination for those seeking more than conventional networking. The novelty and uniqueness of BizConnect can be summarized as follows: 1. Comprehensive suite of tools: BizConnect offers a comprehensive suite of tools that goes beyond traditional networking to facilitate collaboration, knowledgesharing, and rapid business growth among businesses in the technology and innovation sectors. 2. Tailored to specific needs: Unlike competitors that may offer generic networking solutions, BizConnect stands out by tailoring its features to the specific needs of SMEs and startups in the tech industry. Curated content: BizConnect offers curated content that is specifically tailored to address the unique needs of SMEs and startups in the technology and innovation sectors. 3. Industry-specific networking events: The platform offers industry-specific networking events that enable entrepreneurs to connect with like-minded individuals and businesses. 4. Brilliant Differentiation Strategy: BizConnect's Brilliant Differentiation Strategy provides added value that competitors lack and caters

to the target market's desire for a more sophisticated networking experience. 5. User-friendly interface: The interface of BizConnect is clean, modern, and userfriendly, reflecting the professional nature of entrepreneurial endeavors. Profiles are visually appealing, allowing entrepreneurs to highlight their achievements, skills, and ongoing projects.

6. BENEFIT TO MANKIND

BizConnect is a comprehensive platform that goes beyond traditional networking by offering a suite of tools to facilitate collaboration, knowledge sharing, and business growth. The platform features user-friendly profiles, allowing entrepreneurs to showcase their skills, projects, and business ventures. Key features include a dynamic project collaboration space, a resource exchange hub, and an event management system. The platform is tailored to the specific needs of SMEs and startups in the tech industry, providing advanced networking solutions that foster collaboration and innovation. BizConnect offers curated content that is specifically tailored to address the unique needs of SMEs and startups in the technology and innovation sectors, providing valuable insights and knowledge-sharing opportunities. The platform also offers industry-specific networking events that enable entrepreneurs to connect with likeminded individuals and businesses, providing opportunities for growth and expansion. BizConnect's benefits and applications lie in providing a comprehensive networking platform that goes beyond traditional networking to facilitate collaboration, knowledgesharing, and rapid business growth among businesses in the technology and innovation sectors. The platform's tailored features, curated content, industry-specific networking events, and user-friendly interface position it as the premier destination for those seeking more than conventional networking. By connecting entrepreneurs with like-minded individuals and businesses, BizConnect drives innovation and helps businesses stay ahead of the curve. The platform saves time and money by providing a one-stop-shop for networking, collaboration, and knowledge-sharing, eliminating the need for multiple platforms and tools. BizConnect also facilitates collaboration by providing a platform for entrepreneurs to collaborate on projects, share resources, and exchange ideas, fostering a collaborative and supportive community. Overall, BizConnect is a game-changer in the world of networking and collaboration, providing a comprehensive platform that goes beyond traditional networking to facilitate collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and rapid business growth among businesses in the technology and innovation sectors. The platform's tailored features, curated content, industry-specific networking events, and user-friendly interface position it as the premier destination for those seeking more than conventional networking.

7. COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL

BizConnect has enormous potential for commercialization, given its unique features and benefits. The platform is tailored to the specific needs of SMEs and startups in the tech industry, providing advanced networking solutions that foster collaboration and innovation. The platform's tailored features, curated content, industry-specific networking events, and user-friendly interface position it as the premier destination for those seeking more than conventional networking. One potential avenue for commercialization is through the promotion and uptake of premium subscription services. By offering advanced features and exclusive access, the premium subscriptions aim to provide exceptional value to users while contributing significantly to BizConnect's financial success. This revenue stream can be further enhanced by forging strategic partnerships with key industry influencers. These alliances will not only elevate BizConnect's profile but also enhance the overall user experience through curated content and expert insights. Another potential avenue for commercialization is through targeted advertising and sponsorships. BizConnect's event management system facilitates the organization and promotion of networking events, webinars, and workshops.

Integrated communication tools enable real-time interactions between entrepreneurs, making it easier to connect, collaborate, and learn from one another. This presents an opportunity for businesses to advertise their products and services to a highly targeted audience, increasing their visibility and potential customer base. Furthermore, BizConnect can also generate revenue through the sale of data analytics and insights. The platform collects data on user behavior, preferences, and interactions, which can be analyzed to provide valuable insights into market trends and consumer behavior. This data can be sold to businesses looking to gain a competitive edge in their respective industries. In conclusion, BizConnect has enormous potential for commercialization, given its unique features and benefits. The platform's tailored features, curated content, industry-specific networking events, and user-friendly interface position it as the premier destination for those seeking more than conventional networking. By leveraging premium subscription services, targeted advertising and sponsorships, and data analytics and insights, BizConnect can generate significant revenue while providing exceptional value to its users.

8. STATUS OF INNOVATION

Our product is currently in the invention stage and the name of our product is BizConnect which is born out of a commitment to innovation, BizConnect is set to redefine SMEs which is the platform offers easily navigable user profiles, providing entrepreneurs with the opportunity to highlight their expertise, ongoing projects, and business initiatives. Noteworthy components encompass an interactive workspace for project collaboration, a central hub for resource exchange, and a comprehensive system for managing events. This revolutionary creation stems from a fusion of creativity and problem-solving, addressing designed exclusively for SMEs and startups within the technology sector, the platform delivers sophisticated networking solutions to encourage collaborative efforts and innovation. Product invention refers to the process of creating and introducing a new and original product to the market. It involves developing something that is not currently available or significantly improving upon existing products. On the other hand, product invention is a form of innovation that can result in the introduction of novel technologies, designs, functionalities, or features. The term "invention" refers to the active pursuit of developing something novel, often involving the creation of a new process or device (Joshi, 2013) The term "invention" implies a high degree of creativity and uniqueness. It goes beyond mere modifications or incremental improvements to existing products. Successful product inventions often address unmet needs, solve problems, or provide innovative solutions that set them apart in the market. On the contrary, (Scott, 2023) said that inventions result from the innovative arrangement of existing knowledge elements, and the discovery process is inherently uncertain due to the vast array of different knowledge elements available.

9. CONCLUSION

BizConnect serves as an engine for revolutionary advancement in the entrepreneurial area, addressing the lack of comprehensive networking platforms designed specifically for startups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating in the dynamic fields of technology and innovation. Traditional networking platforms frequently fall short in offering the essential tools and functionalities required to facilitate significant collaborations and ensure sustained growth in these constantly evolving sectors. By providing customised solutions that enable startups and SMEs, BizConnect strategically addresses this gap and establishes itself as a key driver of growth and development in the complex realm of innovation and technology. Due to the strategic incorporation of critical features, BizConnect has achieved an exceptional standing in the entrepreneurial landscape. It stands out for its clever incorporation of a resource exchange center, simple profiles, an event management system, and a dynamic project collaboration area. Its user-centric design facilitates the

effective dissemination of information and offerings by providing an efficient and intuitive experience. In contrast with traditional networking platforms, BizConnect expands beyond the limitations of the digital realm by integrating a dynamic arena for project collaboration. By facilitating collaborative involvement, this space for real-time interaction exceeds the constraints of traditional platforms. BizConnect essentially redefines the standard for networking platforms by providing a comprehensive and innovative solution that encourages improved engagement among users and collaboration. The resource exchange center, which is a crucial element of BizConnect, enables SMEs and startups to pool and share resources in an efficient manner. By leveraging on the community's collective strengths, this collaborative ecosystem not only enhances operational efficiency but also encourages innovation. The integrated event management system enhances the accessibility of the platform by establishing a centralised location for the coordination and participation in industry-relevant events. By facilitating shared resources and collaborative events, this dual functionality not only enhances the efficiency of daily operations but also develops a dynamic atmosphere that stimulates creativity and advances in the technology sector. BizConnect is strategically designed to solve the lack of comprehensive networking solutions in the technology and innovation fields through the customisation of features and curation of content. This strategic approach is designed to create an atmosphere that is favourable for substantial collaborations, creative thinking, and long-term growth. BizConnect functions as a unified and comprehensive solution, eliminating the necessity for numerous distinct platforms and tools. This combination makes a substantial contribution to the improvement of the entrepreneurial environment by providing small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and entrepreneurs with the necessary assistance to flourish and achieve success in the complex domain of the digital economy.

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